

The Sacrifice How Pro-Palestine Protests Students are Sacrificing to Change the World?

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Abstract

The recent surge in pro-Palestine student activism has prompted significant responses from universities, ranging from negotiations and divestment commitments to increased transparency about investments in companies supporting the war on Gaza. This activism has led to the cessation of student encampments but also highlighted the substantial sacrifices made by students, including academic disruptions and personal risks. The primary drivers of these protests are poor university administration, lack of transparency, and inadequate communication between officials and students. This study examines the profound emotional, psychological, and professional impacts on students engaged in pro-Palestine protests, focusing on Generation Z's (Gen-Z) activism dynamics. This paper explores the significant sacrifices made by these students and even the professors supporting the pro-Palestine movement, with a focus on recent global movements. Through an in-depth analysis of printed and electronic media, the study examines the impacts of these sacrifices on the academic and personal lives of those involved. The paper highlights examples from various universities, demonstrating student activism's long-term and short-term effects, including disciplinary actions, social backlash, and career implications. The researchers also explore the broader implications of student sacrifices. The findings reveal that these sacrifices are driven by a profound commitment to justice and human rights, and are influenced by the increasing availability of information, peer interactions, and personal convictions. The study also discusses the broader implications of this activism, comparing it to historical precedents and assessing its potential to influence policy and public opinion. The emotional and psychological toll on student activists is significant, but their sense of purpose and community support mitigates some of these challenges. However, the researchers call for acknowledging the broader Impact of these sacrifices on the future global movement of FreePalestine.

Keywords: *Pro-Palestine Student Protests, Sacrifice, Gaza Liberation Movement, University Protests, Generation Z, War on Gaza.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The sacrifices made by the students protesting for the cause of Gaza have made some universities negotiate with the students, including divesting from the companies supporting the war against Gaza. Other universities have decided to disclose the amount of investment in companies engaged in the war against Gaza. As a result, the students have decided to end the encampments.

Education, especially at the university level, plays a significant role in strengthening the wellbeing of society. The students boycotting the classes hamper the completion of courses, which has huge monetary, and psychological consequences on the life of students. The

significant causes of student protests are the poor administration of universities, the lack of transparent policies of the universities, and poor communication between university officials and students. The universities should resort to good administration, transparent policies and effective communication between the university officials and the students. Identifying the comprehensive implications of student protesting, all the partners must categorize the calculated mediations to protect not only the national educational interest but also to safeguard the humanitarian aspect of the society and not let the oppressor further exploit the weaker section of the society. Feinberg, and Salehyan (2023)

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Realising the Change that Started by Pro-Palestine Students

2.1.1 The Changes in the Narrative

The narrative of the War of 2023/2024 on Gaza that started to shape the Gen-Z is that a group of people conspire against the rest of the world to plunder their wealth, steal their lands, or control their energy sources in the name of Zionism and its related allies. A series of different destruction or attacks begin to dominate these oppressed societies with the aim of sabotaging their life systems economically, ideologically, and morally. Those who have values are weak in responding to these conspiracy-based attacks due to their fragmentation and lack of strength. Buheji (2024)

The conspirators are waiting for the opportunity, which they believe is historic, to eliminate their victims forever. An example of this is the idea of displacing two million citizens from Gaza in agreement with the allied Western and certain Arab Governments who normalised the relations with Israel. The narrative says that this is in exchange for its promise to displace more Arabs around Palestine, shape the geopolitical maps and disrupt the demography in the region.

A group of rights holders rise up to defend their rights after they have become aware and realise that the hidden force that runs the universe will be on their side if they rise up in order to change their humiliating reality, despite the material advantage prevailing on the side of their enemies. This group is the generation that has become capable of confrontation, the generation of change, and the generation that was chosen to implement (the Sunnah of Usage). Buheji (2018)

2.1.2 Understanding the Generation-Z relation to the Spirit of Sacrifice

Leading organizations are surprised by the increasing student movements in the USA and the West. Recent surveys at Harvard University show shifting opinions among young Americans regarding the Israeli-Palestinian conflict and the War on Gaza. A national poll by the Institute of Politics at Harvard University (2024) Kennedy School found that over half of young Americans (18-29) plan to vote in the upcoming Presidential election, with varying support levels among subgroups. The Harvard Public Opinion Project (HPOP) has highlighted growing political engagement among young Americans, driven by concerns over the economy, foreign policy, and social issues. Despite the majority still supporting Israel, the Harvard CAPS-Harris survey revealed that support for Palestine and its rights for liberation among Gen Z has increased, with 43% expressing support, compared to 37% in a previous survey. Buheji et al. (2024)

Pro-Palestinian protests have surged on college campuses since the October 7 Hamas attack on Israel, drawing national attention and leading to numerous arrests. Polls indicate that support for Hamas decreases with age, and there is strong support for a permanent ceasefire in Gaza among young Americans. Impelli (2024), Buheji and Hasan (2024b)

A significant portion of Gen-Z believes that the resolution to the conflict requires the disappearance of the State of Israel, with support for Palestinian resistance growing. This shift in beliefs has alarmed the ruling elite in the USA, as it contrasts sharply with traditional Western views. Harvard University (2024)

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Another poll by The Economist showed scepticism among Generation Z about the historical narrative of the Holocaust, with many doubting its occurrence or viewing the accounts as exaggerated. This has raised concerns about the influence of social media and the need for educational intervention. The Economist (2023)

2.1.3 The Counter-movement to the Sacrificers

The counter-movement might invent humanitarian, environmental, or health disasters to distract public opinion from the Palestinian issue, such as initiating a side war or causing a catastrophe. The counter-movement ignites regional, political, or religious strife among Palestinians to undermine their credibility and portray their cause as unjust.

Supporters of the resistance party must impose the reality of differentiation in different arenas on the basis of supporters and opponents. This means the reclassification of social, economic, and political forces on the basis of supporting or opposing the rights of the Palestinian people.

Such a new reality will impose a new chain of loyalties, and break an old chain of loyalties that were based on people following the major bodies and groups that control the world with their names, brands, records, fame, assets, and platforms. Boren (2013).

2.2 Realising the Solidarity of a Movement that is willing to Sacrifice

2.2.1 A Movement with Clear Main Unified Value

The flow of high values coming from Gaza, defending their existence, their land and their community, have been resonating with this Gen-Z who feels too that they have been cheated, let down similar to those suffering displacement, or being marginalized by the deep Zionist system in the Western Society, Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024). This has created new communities that, although helpless themselves, sympathize with these struggles and provide aid and logistical support. This support is manifested through daily peaceful demonstrations in Europe, America, and some Asian capitals, as well as economic boycotts against entities and companies supporting the perpetrators of violence and oppression. Buheji and Ahmed (2023)

Activists are leveraging alternative media to raise awareness and mobilize public opinion. In the USA, young and educated generations are confronting blatant human rights violations and advocating for the right to life. These young activists are at the forefront of shaping public opinion, leading protests and strikes at 250 university campuses, including some of the most prestigious institutions, demanding justice. Buheji and Hasan (2024b)

Immigrants who have long had platforms in Western countries are finding a new audience eager to learn about the issue and its history, and even to explore Islam. These new supporters are receptive to calls for change, embracing the cause with conviction and passion before preachers and speakers even begin to address them. They are convinced of the need for change, which deeply resonates with their own lives.

The recent surge in student activism can be attributed to a growing disillusionment among young people with the contradictions they perceive in their political, academic, and commercial systems. Generation Z, which places a high value on justice, transparency, and authenticity, finds the support for the Israeli occupation by their institutions and governments to be hypocritical. They reject the crimes committed in their name, whether through university investments, government taxes, or political stances. The powerful rallying cry of "Not in our name" reflects their determination to dissociate from actions they view as unjust. Buheji and Ahmed (2017)

2.2.2 A Movement that Appreciates History of the Role of Students to Mobilise Change Cycles in the World

The university student movement coincided with the black liberation movement of the 1960s and positively impacted achieving victory. However, the largest student movement came in 1970 when students demonstrated at Kent State University - Ohio, in opposition to the war in Vietnam. The police opened fire on them, killing four and wounding nine. Four million students went on strike, which was the largest demonstration shock in the country's history. Then Nixon came after it and ended the war. Boren (2013).

After years of internal American political disputes over the future of the apartheid regime in South Africa and student demonstrations, Berkeley University decided to withdraw its investments from South Africa in 1978, and about 156 American universities followed suit. Thus, economic and political pressures increased until the apartheid regime fell. Buheji and Hasan (2024c)

Immediately after October 7, 4 out of 200 members of Congress voted in Favor of the Palestinian resistance's right to defend itself, and then the votes began to increase. It should be known that 4.5 million voters who are biased toward Israel in American society are Jews in origin. While tens of millions of voters who are biased toward Israel are Christian Zionists who believe in the coming of the Savior, and believe that only 144,000 Jews will turn into Christians at the end of time, and that the rest will disappear.

This new generation's commitment to their principles has led to a robust and widespread movement demanding change, justice, and accountability. Their activism signifies a significant shift in public opinion and political engagement, highlighting the increasing influence of younger generations in shaping the future.

2.2.3 A Movement that Realises a Lifetime Opportunity

These are rare opportunities that activists, oppressed communities and advocates of change cannot afford to miss or neglect. This is a chance to debunk the false narrative of the usurping entity that has deceived the global masses for decades. The Israeli entity uses this myth to manipulate and attract sympathy for their alleged cause.

There is an opportunity to unveil the global political and economic conspiracies that undermine human freedoms and rebuild national wealth. This is a crucial moment to elevate awareness among people and societies about their rightful claims to life, and self-

determination. Colonizing countries have exploited these resources since the era of colonialism.

This is an opportunity to challenge the negative exploitation of laws that control public freedoms. Laws against anti-Semitism, intellectual terrorism, and defamation of religion are often misused to serve specific interests, and this moment can help to correct these abuses.

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2.2.4 Growing Disillusionment about Transparency of the Western Countries about the Palestine Issue

Every civilization defends its ideology, and American civilization has long been distinguished by its Constitution, which guarantees public freedoms, democracy, the rule of law, and individual privacy. However, the United States is also built on economic, political, and national interests that are deeply intertwined with the ruling elite's interests.

When these interests align with constitutional principles, there is no conflict. But when they clash, public freedoms are often compromised to protect elite interests. Generation Z university students have become acutely aware of this hypocrisy.

In the 1980s, persistent demonstrations against apartheid in South Africa led to significant actions, such as Berkeley University and 156 other universities divesting from companies supporting the apartheid regime. This contributed to the fall of apartheid in South Africa. Today, American university students are taking a similar stand against their country's support for Israel. Motivated by a strong sense of justice, they demand that universities divest from investments in companies that manufacture weapons for Israel, not wanting to be complicit in the oppression or apartheid.

The endowments of American universities are substantial, totalling about \$450 billion among the 20 largest universities. Suppose students succeed in their divestment campaigns at one university. Others are likely to follow in that case, leading to a domino effect that could significantly impact Israeli policies by reducing investment and forcing stock prices to fall. This potential economic impact is a major concern for the Israeli entity. Buheji and Hasan (2024c), Lozano (2024)

As students learn more about the origins of the Palestinian issue, their understanding deepens, and their anger grows. They uncover historical inaccuracies, media biases, the influence of capital in decision-making, and the Zionist lobby's control over legislation in Congress. This has sparked a broad movement of rejection, starting from street protests to boycotts of goods, social media campaigns, and university actions, extending even to the cultural boycott of celebrities and artists who remain silent on the issue.

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2.3 Appreciating the Level and Types of Sacrifice by the Pro-Palestine Students

2.3.1 Source of Students Strong Belief that Raise the Level of Sacrifice

The availability of information and self-education has empowered individuals to become more informed about global issues. Interaction with Arab, Muslim, and Palestinian students has also played a crucial role in fostering a climate of respect for human dignity and support for the oppressed. This influence extends even to Jewish students, who, despite their Zionist backgrounds, are affected by peer pressure and the moral arguments of their peers. This has led to Jewish students participating in demonstrations, challenging the actions of the ruling elite.

Students studying human values and principles are often shocked by the violence and injustices supported by their universities. This has led to powerful demonstrations with slogans like "Do not kill in our name." Many students feel a deep moral obligation to participate in movements against current injustices, driven by the desire to be on the right side of history.

The endowments of American universities are another source of students' belief in making a difference. They believe that starting a movement for divestment from Israel can stop contracts of more than \$450 billion among the 20 largest universities. These students believe that their divestment success, even at one university, others are likely to follow, leading to a domino effect that could significantly impact Israeli policies by reducing investment and forcing stock prices to fall. This potential economic impact is a major concern for the Israeli entity.

Progressive movements have been effective in exposing media falsehoods and political hypocrisy, as seen in historical precedents like the Iraq War and the fight against terrorism in Afghanistan. This has led to widespread distrust of media figures and political officials, prompting students to seek information independently.

2.3.2 Hopes of Students Sacrificing for Pro-Palestine Protests

No doubt that the Pro-Palestine students who engage in activism and make significant sacrifices are driven by a range of hopes and aspirations. These personal and collective hopes reflect their desire for justice, change, and a better future. Buheji (2020a)

Hope is important, as it brings determination and dedication to the cause one is fighting for. Despite the challenges, many students feel a deep sense of hope and determination. The belief that their actions can contribute to meaningful change sustains their efforts and provides emotional resilience, Buheji (2020a). Besides, whether through protests, education, or advocacy, taking action can lead to feelings of empowerment and a sense of purpose. Buheji (2020a)

Students hope is also to see an end to the oppression and injustices faced by Palestinians. They are driven by the belief that their efforts can help bring about significant changes in the lives of those suffering under occupation. They aim for international recognition and respect for Palestinian human rights, ensuring that the basic rights and dignity of Palestinian people are upheld.

The rising awareness about Palestinian rights and the changing narratives are making Gen-Z students get even more involved in the importance of this global awareness. They believe that educating others and spreading information can shift public opinion and generate broader support. This makes these students aim to challenge and change the prevailing

misconceptions and biased narratives about Palestinians and their struggle, promoting a more accurate and empathetic understanding of the conflict. Buheji et al. (2024)

There is also a hope that these students influence policymakers to adopt more just and equitable policies regarding the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. By demanding divestment and changes in university policies, they aim to hold institutions accountable for their financial and political support of oppressive regimes. This includes pushing for government actions that support Palestinian rights and oppose occupation.

The other hope of all hopes is that this student generation believes in building a strong sense of solidarity among diverse groups, including fellow students, faculty, and the broader community for the cause. They believe that unified support can amplify their impact. Therefore, they strive to empower Palestinian voices, ensuring that those who are directly affected by the conflict have a platform to share their stories and advocate for their rights. This hope is motivated by maintaining their moral and ethical integrity, i.e. living according to values and beliefs, and feeling that their activism is a necessary expression of their commitment to justice. This hope has built among them a sense of purpose and fulfilment. They hope their actions, even if small, contribute to a larger movement for change. Buheji (2020a), Buheji (2019)

These students know that they are living in a defining moment where they can create a legacy and impact future generations' fate. They hope to be part of a historical movement that brings about meaningful change. They aspire to leave a legacy of activism and advocacy that future generations can build upon. With this attitude and thinking, they aim to inspire other young people to engage in social justice causes, fostering a culture of activism and responsibility among future generations.

The hopes of students sacrificing for Pro-Palestine protests are deeply rooted in their desire for justice, human rights, and meaningful change. They aim to raise awareness, influence policies, build solidarity, and maintain moral integrity. These students are driven by the belief that their efforts can contribute to a better future for Palestinians and set a precedent for global activism and justice. Their commitment and sacrifices reflect a profound hope for a world where oppression is challenged, and human dignity is upheld.

2.3.3 Type of Sacrifices and Potential Effects

Pro-Palestine student protesters often face significant sacrifices and challenges due to their activism. These sacrifices can impact their academic experiences, professional futures, and personal lives. Students might face disciplinary actions from their universities for participating in protests, especially if these protests are seen as disruptive. This can include warnings, suspensions, or even expulsion in extreme cases. Activism can be time-consuming and emotionally draining, potentially affecting students' academic performance and focus on their studies. Buheji and Hasan (2024b)

Participation in protests and being involved in controversial movements can show up in background checks, potentially influencing employers' perceptions and hiring decisions. Professional networks may be strained, especially if potential employers or colleagues hold opposing views on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. This can limit job opportunities and career advancement.

The Gen-Z's statements reflect their feelings towards the Palestinian people and their resistance. Some Gen-Z mentions that they see that the Palestinians "don't despair about this

life; the only one they fear is God, and they keep saying: God is all-knowing". Others see Palestinians "embodying the patience and resilience described in the Bible".

Generation Z, in particular, is drawn to heroic and courageous stances. They admire the resilience and effectiveness of the Palestinian resistance, which, despite severe constraints, continues to challenge a technologically superior enemy. News of such steadfastness and courage ignites their enthusiasm to support justice and human rights, further fueling their activism.

2.3.4 Students Sacrifice vs. Social Isolation and Stigmatization

Activism can strain relationships with peers who either oppose the pro-Palestine stance or prefer to remain apolitical. This can lead to social isolation and a sense of being marginalized within their own community. Students might face backlash on social media and in public, including harassment and threats, which can affect their mental health and sense of safety.

Participation in protests can sometimes lead to arrests, requiring students to deal with legal proceedings and potential fines or other penalties. Legal battles can be costly and stressful. Activism, particularly if it leads to disciplinary actions, might jeopardize scholarships and financial aid, increasing the financial burden on students and their families, thus increasing their social isolation further.

These students' strong political stances might lead to feelings of alienation, especially if their views are not widely accepted within their immediate social circles or academic environments. It is alarming that these students feel alienated from institutions they perceive as complicit in the injustices they are fighting against, leading to disconnection from their educational environment.

2.3.5 Sacrifice vs. Emotional and Psychological Exposure on Pro-Palestine Students

The pressures of activism, combined with potential harassment and threats, can lead to significant stress, anxiety, and other mental health issues. This sustained activism can result in burnout, affecting students' overall wellbeing and ability to maintain their academic and personal responsibilities. Moiz. (2024)

When a young generation of Gen-Z students gets engaged in activism, particularly around contentious and deeply personal issues such as the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, it could create on them significant emotional and psychological impacts. For example, it's could create for them a level of intense empathy. This type of empathy develops from the constant exposure to stories of suffering and injustice can lead to overwhelming feelings of empathy. Students often identify deeply with the struggles of the Palestinian people, which can lead to emotional exhaustion. This might create a type of compassion fatigue, where students feel drained and find it harder to maintain their level of emotional support and activism. Buheji and Ahmed (2024)

The other source of emotional or psychological pressures comes from feelings of anger and frustration. Witnessing or learning about the injustices faced by Palestinians can evoke strong feelings of anger and frustration. This anger is often directed at perceived perpetrators, including governments, institutions, and sometimes peers who do not share their views. The slow pace of change and the feeling that their efforts may not be making a significant difference can lead to frustration and a sense of helplessness.

Besides the high levels of stress and anxiety, many of these students are living in a state of uncertainty about the Impact of their actions and potential negative consequences on their future careers and personal lives. These moral dilemmas make the students experience cognitive dissonance, where their actions or the actions of their peers conflict with their moral beliefs. This occurs specifically when protests turn violent or when they face backlash from family or community members beyond expected. The continuous engagement with complex issues may lead students to question their own values and beliefs, leading to internal conflict and stress. Buheji et al. (2024)

2.4.6 Doxxing as a Sample of Pro-Palestine Protesters' Sacrifice

Yes, Pro-Palestine protesters, particularly university students, are facing doxxing and significant backlash. Several incidents have been reported where students involved in pro-Palestine activism were targeted with doxxing, which involves the malicious public release of private or identifying information. This has led to severe consequences for those affected.

At Harvard University, for example, a conservative media group displayed a billboard truck showing the names and faces of students labelled as "Harvard's Leading Antisemites" following a pro-Palestine statement. This created significant safety concerns and led to emotional distress among the students involved. Many reported feeling scared and stressed; some even had to inform their families about the potential dangers posed by these doxxing actions, Kumar (2024).

Furthermore, at the University of Texas, students participating in pro-Palestine protests expressed fears of being doxxed. They reported altering their online presence to avoid being targeted, which underscores the anxiety and precautionary measures taken by students involved in activism, McDaniel (2024).

This doxxing has had professional ramifications as well. Some students have lost job offers or face challenges in pursuing careers in the United States due to being associated with pro-Palestine activities. This has prompted calls for greater support from universities to protect their students from such harassment and its long-term impacts on their lives and careers, Kim and Montgomery (2023).

Overall, the emotional and psychological toll of doxxing on these students is significant, affecting their sense of security, professional opportunities, and mental wellbeing. The ongoing issue highlights the need for institutional support and protective measures for student activists.

2.4 Future Foresight for this Sacrifice Impact

Future foresight relies on an assessment of the present reality, which involves gathering information about current and recent economic, social, educational, and political conditions. This data is used to create predictive models of future conditions. However, an unquantifiable factor also plays a crucial role: the human aspect, which encompasses the release of human energy towards rejection and change when individuals face challenging environmental choices. This response is influenced by factors such as willpower, hope, values, dignity, awareness, and spiritual connection to a higher power. Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024)

Human energy can sometimes outweigh the burdens of living, leading to efforts to shape a new future through unexpected humanitarian movements. For example, in the labour market, universities, and academies, individuals often face environmental challenges that ignite their will to change their reality, achieve the impossible, and succeed, as evidenced by numerous stories of famous and successful people throughout history. Ahmed et al. (2020)

At the social level, shared conditions such as witnessing the atrocities created by humans on follow humans as the war on Gaza, can provoke collective human energy towards change, manifesting as revolutions, uprisings, or other social movements, Buheji (2024), Snow et al. (2004). The timing and extent of these movements are unpredictable, governed by a hidden force that orchestrates the events of the universe according to universal and divine laws. These laws, which support the weak, advocate for the oppressed, and impose justice, often defy human plans and expectations. Buheji and Hasan (2024a)

The most important arenas in which differentiation can occur in the future are the arena of consumption of economic goods, using the economic boycott methodology, which is for a group of platforms and committees of activists to undertake the boycott methodology and pay attention to all its details in boycotting consumer goods whose producers have proven to support the usurping entity. Buheji and Ahmed (2023)

The entertainment and arts arena, by boycotting celebrities who supported the usurping criminal in its mass massacres, by boycotting their accounts on social media, their works, and their products. Those who have been silent about protesting crimes can declare their positions. Buheji and Hasan (2024b)

The other arena, the sports and games arena, by boycotting sports celebrities who supported crime and allowing those who remained silent about it. The arena of famous media platforms, boycotting content makers who supported crime and giving an opportunity to those who remained silent about it. Buheji and Ahmed (2023)

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The paper studies the in-depth analysis of the print and electronic media all across the globe and especially in the USA about the sacrifices made by the students and professors to support the cause of Gaza. Further analysis has been carried out to study the Impact of the sacrifices made by the students and professors all across the global universities towards the liberation of Gaza.

4.0 APPLICATION & ANALYSIS

4.1 Examples of Sacrifices and Challenges for Pro-Palestine Protests

There is really an amazing case of sacrifices made by the students involved in pro-Palestine activism. The students have faced disciplinary hearings and social backlash at the University of California (UC), Berkeley. These students often have to balance their activism with their academic responsibilities, which can be challenging and exhausting. At Columbia University, pro-Palestine student activists have reported feeling marginalized and facing administrative pushback. Despite these challenges, they continued to advocate for their cause, highlighting the sacrifices they made for their beliefs. Times of Israel (2024)

4.1.1 Long-Term Effects

One of the main sacrifices that these students are making is their activism record. Hence, while some employers may value the leadership and dedication shown by student activists, others might view their involvement in controversial issues as a liability, potentially affecting long-term career prospects. However, this activism might also open new opportunities that develop the students' networking. Such activism can both open doors within certain

professional circles and close them in others, depending on the political and social views prevalent in the industry.

4.1.2 Short-Term Effects

Students who receive scholarships from prestigious universities rarely want to risk their opportunities and future employment due to a changing landscape of awareness and culture. This means the student would usually try to abide by the university rules, from the time of acceptance until graduation. This was not the case for the new generation that believed that this is a defining moment where they sacrificed all the short-term processes, whether at the university's entry stage or at the graduation ceremony.

Therefore, it is not surprising to hear that many graduates didn't attend the graduation ceremony, or they sacrificed being prevented from receiving their certificates because they interrupted the ceremony with their Pro Palestine peers, raising slogans such as "how do you spell justice" Boycott Divest & Sanction". In other universities, students in the graduating ceremonies protested by staging a walkout against the guest speakers who had been sympathizing with Israel. These short-term sacrifices are more than can be listed in this paper; however, in Table (1), we list the most important ones that we expect as authors to have an effect on the future of the protests.

Table (1): Type of Sacrifices by the Students as per the University type

Name of University	Type of Sacrifice the Students Gone through
University of California, Berkeley	At the graduation ceremony of Berkeley the graduating students walked across the stage waving the Palestinian flag and carrying Keffiyeh as a symbol of protest against Israel for their ongoing war in Gaza. There were also some students who were against the Pro Gaza student supporters. According to Michaela Forouzan, a Berkeley graduating student, said that she could not hear the speakers due to the Pro Gaza supporters, and all her hard work for the last 4 years seems to have been wasted. According to Eduardo Realegeno, a Berkeley graduating student said that he is neither a Palestinian supporter or an Israeli supporter, but he does not like the idea of people killing people. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EOFJJYVpR2w
University of California, Berkeley	Professor Catherine Frisk and her dean husband Erwin Chemerinsky hosted a dinner for graduating law students at the University of California, Berkeley. Malak Afaneh, a Palestinian student, started to speak for the cause of the Gaza people when her microphone was snatched by Professor Catherine Frisk and taken out of the party. Lozano (2024).
Duke University	Comedian Jerry Seinfeld, who has been a staunch supporter of Israel, was received with some boos at the graduation ceremony of Duke University.
University of Illinois, Chicago	A graduating student by the name of Ayesha Affaneh dedicated her speech to Gaza and urged to divest from the companies that are helping Israel in committing genocide against Gaza. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y2-K1wLg-CU
University of California, Los Angeles	According to Ryan, an English major student at the University of California, Los Angeles, he was hit by batons by the cops. He further said that the police tried to intimidate the students rather than thinking about the divestment from the companies supporting Israel in the war against Gaza. He said that 25 students were hospitalized due to an attack by pro Israel supporters. However, the pro-Israeli students were not arrested. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JE7QLVara8M
University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill	Gabe, a senior at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, was suspended from the university from taking exams or graduating for

	protesting genocide in Gaza, had decided to organize the graduation ceremony at an alternate venue. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wo0a2CsPhjg
University of Amsterdam	The Netherland police used a bulldozer to evacuate the pro-Palestinian protesters and remove the barricades from the University of Amsterdam, and police also detained around 140 people when the protest turned violent at the University of Amsterdam https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=K3WYqztzjcw
Arizona State University	A Muslim pro-Palestinian protester was harassed by Jonathan Yudelman, a Jew and professor of Political Theory at Arizona State University, later on he was suspended from the University https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7HtusnhA1yw (Moiz (2024).
University of Manchester	A Palestinian student, Dana Abuqamar of Manchester University, who studied law and was also a Friends of Palestine Society leader, revoked her student visa when she made a speech citing national security issues at the university demonstration. Ullah (2024).
Jawahar Lal Nehru University,India	Delhi police arrested 60 students for participating in a pro-Gaza protest in New Delhi, India. Wion. (2023).
Kolkata, India	Thousands of students and teachers staged a protest against the war of Israel against Gaza. Chakraborty (2023).
Karachi, Pakistan	Hundreds of students took part in the protest to end the genocide in Gaza in reference to the 76 years of the Palestinians displaced from their homeland. Khan (2024)
Montgomery Country Public Schools(MCPS), Maryland,USA	A black Muslim Arab American middle school teacher was put on administrative leave due to her support for Palestine. Times of India. (2024).
University of Melbourne, Australia	The pro-Gaza protesters protesting at the University of Melbourne would be subject to police action if they continue to protest. Cassidy and Ittimani (2024).
University of Auckland, New Zealand	Peaceful and Lawful protest had been organized at the University of Auckland, New Zealand. (Watson 2024).

4.2 The Academics Sacrifices for Pro-Palestine Protests

Besides the students' sacrifice, the academic sacrifice supported the student pro-Palestine protests and, as the authors believe, had a role in creating its momentum. It is worth mentioning that since the War on Gaza in October 2023, many academicians all over the world have either been fired or suspended due to being pro-Gaza or calling for stopping the genocide in Gaza. Table (2) gives a glimpse of some of the sacrifices made by the academic staff.

Table (2): Type of Sacrifices by the Academics as per the University type

Name of University	Type of Sacrifice the Academics Gone through
University of Columbia	Professor Mohammad Abdou, a visiting professor in Modern Arab Studies at Columbia University, was fired after his pro-Gaza remarks. Times of Israel Staff. (2024).
University of Illinois	A pro-Palestine professor of history Steve Tamari at Southern Illinois University Edwardsville was beaten by police and was arrested and has multiple rib fractures. India Today World Desk. (2024).
University of California	Tiffany Willoughby-Herard, an African American studies professor at the University of California,Irvine, was arrested after a fiery speech by her. The New Arab Staff (2024).
University of Washington	Nine University of Washington professors were suspended for their pro-Gaza protest. Barczewski (2024).
Dartmouth College, New Hampshire	A 65-year-old Professor Annelise Orleck, head of Jewish studies at Dartmouth College,New Hampshire was arrested for Pro Gaza protest. Times Now World Desk (2024).

	An English teacher in the UK was dismissed for her pro Gaza comments during a class debate. World Socialist Website. (2024).
National Education Union Conference, UK	Teachers at the National Education Union Conference, UK have stood up for the Gaza cause and have voted for a motion against Israel. Weale (2024).
Open letter by Australian academicians and staff	An open letter by more than 1,000 academicians and staff was signed in support of the protesting students for Gaza at various universities of Australia. Evans (2024).
Teachers and School Staff for Palestine, Victoria, Australia	The ANZAC day was boycotted by the Teachers and School Staff for Palestine, Victoria Australia as the ANZAC troops were involved in the division of the Arab territories. News.com.au (2024).
Diocesan School, New Zealand	A Diocesan school teacher had sent an email to the students asking them to gather for the Gaza cause. The school authorities later recalled the email stating that the school does not endorse the teacher's personal views. Radio New Zealand (2023).
Josh Hawley, a United States senator	Ryan, Josh Hawley a United States senator from Missouri questions Maria Gabriela Pacheco, president and CEO of dream.us that why the pro Palestinian students should not be deported from United States. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w5u1c8o_KS8

4.3 Formula of Change and the Demand of Sacrifice

The pursuit of change, especially in the context of social and political movements, often follows a specific formula that requires significant sacrifice. This formula can be observed in the actions and attitudes of Generation Z, particularly those engaged in the pro-Palestinian movement.

Gen-Z leverages the abundance of information available through the internet and social media to educate themselves on global issues. They go beyond mainstream narratives to understand conflicts' deeper context and history, such as the Israeli-Palestinian situation. Besides, the increasing interactions with Arab, Muslim, and Palestinian peers provided firsthand perspectives and fostered empathy, leading to a more profound understanding of the issues at hand.

The inherent values that Gen-Z hold and their strong beliefs in justice, human rights, and equality make even their statements full of admiration for the resilience and faith of the Palestinian people. They see them as embodying virtues of patience, hope, and unwavering faith in God, which resonate deeply with their own values. And this is part of the formula for supporting change. Buheji (2020a)

4.4 The Demand of Sacrifice Surrounding Pro-Palestine Students

Achieving meaningful change requires a substantial variety of sacrifices. The top type of sacrifice demand is the personal risks, including potential damage to their academic and professional futures, and, in some cases, physical risks during demonstrations. Social consequences include strained relationships with family and peers who may not share their views or support their activism. Cassidy et al. (2024)

Activists must also dedicate considerable time and energy to organizing and participating in protests, educating themselves and others, and campaigning for change.

Pro-Palestine student protesters face various pressures that can significantly impact their personal, academic, and professional lives. These pressures come from different sources, including institutional policies, societal backlash, peer relationships, and internal struggles.

One of the main pressures on these students is coming from the university, where they most probably face disciplinary actions from their universities for participating in protests or disruptive actions. This can include warnings, suspensions, deportation, or expulsions, affecting their academic records and future educational opportunities. Besides, the administrative pushback as the pressures to refrain from activism to avoid controversy and maintain donor relations are another type of pressure. [Areeb Ullah \(2024\)](#)

The other main source of pressure comes from the family and close community. Some students have faced pressure from family members who disapprove of their activism due to differing political beliefs or concerns about potential repercussions. This might and can create conflict within the family and add emotional stress. Also, such sacrifice and commitment can lead to tensions within broader community groups, especially if these groups have diverse opinions on the issue. Thus, this can affect the student's sense of belonging and support.

Some students are already having personal pressures to strained relationships with peers who hold opposing views or prefer to remain apolitical. This social isolation can lead to a sense of marginalization within their own communities. In the same time, the harassment and threats these students they are facing both online and offline are raising their concerns of personal safety and surely having a direct impact on their mental wellbeing. This can also include social media attacks and doxxing, where personal information is shared publicly to intimidate or harass. [Cassidy et al. \(2024\)](#)

The constant pressure of activism, coupled with backlash and potential threats, can lead to significant stress and anxiety. This can affect students' mental health and academic performance. This creates another pressure that comes from balancing activism with academic demands, which can be particularly challenging and exhausting.

The other last but not least source of pressure on these students are the financial burdens that comes from the legal proceedings and potentially paying fines or legal fees that they would have carried due to their participation in the protests or the encampment.

This might be very challenging, especially if these students risk jeopardizing scholarships and financial aid.

4.5 What Resonates Within Students' Hearts and Minds that Make Them Sacrifice or Risk Their Future?

Pro-Palestine student protesters are driven by deep-seated beliefs, emotional connections, and a strong sense of moral responsibility in their hearts and minds. One could confirm that several key factors contribute to such willingness to sacrifice and risk their futures for such a cause. The most important factor, as per the authors' analysis, comes from these students' inspiring motivation for a strong sense of justice that builds their persistence in standing against what they perceive as egregious human rights violations. They see the plight of Palestinians as a fundamental issue of human rights and feel morally compelled to take action. [Buheji \(2022\)](#)

This resonance might have increased with the accelerated awareness among Gen-Z, specifically about the historical and ongoing injustices against Palestinians, including displacement and military aggression, fuels a determination to seek justice and redress these wrongs.

The other factor for this resonance is their connections and empathy with the personal stories inside Palestine. These students' exposure to personal stories and testimonies from Palestinians, whether through social media, documentaries, or direct interactions, fosters a deep

sense of empathy. Students feel a personal connection to those suffering and are driven by a desire to help and show solidarity. Buheji and Ahmed (2024)

Many students view the Palestinian struggle as part of a broader global movement for justice, aligning it with other social justice causes such as Black Lives Matter. This is an important factor that makes sense of their level of sacrifice. This intersectional approach strengthens their resolve to act in solidarity with oppressed communities worldwide.

Since Higher Education Institutes (HEI's) in the West especially encourage critical thinking and awareness of global issues, courses on Middle Eastern politics, international relations, and human rights have inspired many students to engage deeply with the Palestinian cause. Besides, being part of activist groups and networks, such as Students for Justice in Palestine (SJP), provides a supportive community that reinforces their commitment and offers resources and platforms for activism. The university setting, with its emphasis on debate, critical inquiry, and social responsibility, provides a fertile ground for activism. Academic discussions and campus events focused on the Palestinian issue can inspire students to take action. Buheji and Ahmed (2017)

The other factor that amplified Gen Z's willingness to sacrifice for the pro-Palestine movement was the social media platforms like Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok, which played a crucial role in spreading awareness and mobilizing action. Viral content, hashtags like FreePalestine, and real-time updates from conflict zones make the issues more immediate and compelling. Students often turn to alternative media sources for perspectives they feel are underrepresented in mainstream media, further informing and solidifying their views on the conflict. The other factor that resonates with the Gen-Z are the cultural programs and events, such as Palestinian film festivals, art exhibits, and lectures, which deepen students' understanding and emotional connection to the cause. Snow et al. (2004)

Many of Pro-Palestine students feel that standing up for Palestinian rights is consistent with their broader ethical and political beliefs, such as anti-racism, anti-colonialism, and anti-imperialism. Such commitment provides a sense of purpose and fulfilment, as students feel they are contributing to a cause larger than themselves and making a meaningful impact on the world. Buheji (2019)

4.6 Why Pro-Palestine Students/Academics Are Sacrificing Their Future Despite Not Being Palestinians?

Pro-Palestine students and academics, regardless of their background, are often deeply motivated by a sense of justice, solidarity, and ethical responsibility. This type of new generation is willing to risk their academic and professional futures due to their profound commitment to universal human rights and social justice. They see the Palestinian struggle as part of a broader fight against oppression, occupation, and apartheid, which resonates with their ethical and moral beliefs. Their activism is often rooted in a desire to stand against injustice wherever it occurs. World Socialist Website. (2024)

These students feel a moral obligation to support Palestinians, viewing their plight as emblematic of broader struggles against colonialism and imperialism. They believe their privilege or relatively secure position imposes a duty to speak out and act in solidarity with less fortunate people. They are influenced by educators, peers, and movements that prioritize standing up for oppressed groups. Universities often provide a fertile ground for being involved with global issues and the formation of strong ethical convictions to other fellow humans.

For some students, supporting the Palestinian cause is intertwined with their own personal or political identities. This could be influenced by their own experiences with discrimination or oppression or by their political beliefs that advocate for anti-imperialism, anti-racism, and anti-colonialism. This is especially true in an increasingly connected world, and information about global injustices is more accessible. This global awareness fosters a sense of responsibility and urgency to act on behalf of those who are suffering.

Historical figures like Nelson Mandela, and contemporary movements for social justice, provide inspirational examples of how individuals and groups have successfully fought against oppressive regimes. These examples serve as a reminder that significant change often requires sacrifice and courage.

In certain universities, such as the University of Columbia, the academic curricula might include studies of colonialism, human rights, and international relations, often exposing students to the complexities and injustices of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. This educational background can inspire students to become active advocates for change.

Deep-seated moral and ethical beliefs compel many students to act. They may believe that remaining silent or passive in the face of what they perceive as injustice is morally unacceptable. Their actions are a reflection of their commitment to their values, even at the cost of personal and professional risks. Besides, the influence of broader social movements, such as the global BDS (Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions) movement, provides a framework and support network for students. Being part of a larger movement can amplify their impact and provide a sense of community and purpose. Buheji (2019)

5.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 The Depth of the Students' Sacrifice and its Impact on the Future of Pro-Palestine

Pro-Palestine student protesters make significant sacrifices, including facing academic and career repercussions, social isolation, financial and legal risks, and emotional and psychological impacts. Despite these challenges, their commitment to activism reflects a strong dedication to their beliefs, though it can influence their future opportunities and overall wellbeing.

The willingness of pro-Palestine student protesters to sacrifice and risk their futures is rooted in a complex interplay of justice, empathy, solidarity, political awareness, media influence, educational environment, and personal values. These factors collectively inspire a profound commitment to the Palestinian cause, driving students to engage in activism despite the potential consequences.

Pro-Palestine students' sacrifices are fuelled by a combination of ethical convictions, solidarity with the oppressed, educational influences, and a commitment to social justice. Despite the potential risks to their futures, they are driven by a profound sense of responsibility to stand against what they perceive as grave injustices. Their activism exemplifies the power of global awareness and the enduring impact of solidarity in the fight for human rights.

Pro-Palestine student protesters face a wide range of pressures that impact various aspects of their lives. These include institutional pressures such as disciplinary actions and administrative pushback, social and peer pressures leading to isolation and harassment, career and professional challenges, family and community pressures, internal psychological struggles,

and legal and financial risks. Despite these significant challenges, many students remain committed to their activism, driven by a deep sense of justice, empathy, and solidarity.

The formula of change is inherently tied to the demand for sacrifice. Generation Z's commitment to social justice, particularly in the context of the Palestinian cause, exemplifies how awareness, moral conviction, activism, and personal sacrifice converge to drive movements for change. Their actions are about opposing injustice and building a future aligned with their ethical values and beliefs. Despite the personal costs, this relentless pursuit of justice underscores the transformative potential of a generation determined to make a difference.

5.2 The Depth of the Academics' Sacrifice need more dedicated Research

The sacrifices made by the professors worldwide for the cause of Gaza is a clear indication of how the human sacrifices by the people of Gaza can have a meaningful impact on intellectuals such as academicians. History shows that when these academics start to move, the opinions of the public shake up with these intellectuals, and they start searching for the truth. The sacrifices made by the professors would have an impact on the unresolved issues faced by the citizens of the occupied territories of Palestine. It would surely move the waters in the future towards more FreePalestine policies or at least policies that would shift from the current bias from the occupying forces led by Israel. The authors recommend conducting further research in this line of study. Scholars Against the War on Palestine (2024), Times of Israel (2024), Times of India. (2024), World Socialist Website. (2024), Toloudis, N. (2008).

5.3 Students' Personal Motivations and Visualisation of Change Formula

A significant portion of Generation Z believes that the resolution to the conflict requires the disappearance of the State of Israel, with support for Palestinian resistance growing. This shift in beliefs has alarmed the ruling elite in the USA, as it contrasts sharply with traditional Western views. Such change surely would be faced by US, Israel and their allies through counter-change strategies. Therefore, Gen-Z pro-Palestine protesters need not only to depend on empathetic motivation for supporting FreePalestine, but also an effective strategy for both creating change and managing the change to overcome the coming counter-change by Pro-Israel allies. Buheji (2018)

The Formula of Change = pain x Vision x First Steps of Change, or shortly $C=P \times V \times F$. The amount of pain represented through the level of sacrifice is not enough to bring the change; it needs to be accompanied by the management of vision and planned change management processes in the next three to five years. Only through this would the sacrifice bring further effect and would sustain. This needs to be kept in mind by every Pro-Palestine Encampment Protest leader on every campus, who is expected to make a network of exchanges about the progress of this change process to mitigate risks of counter-change. Buheji (2018)

5.4 Mitigation of Psychological Risks by Keeping the Sense of Community Support and Value of Sacrifice

The emotional and psychological impacts on pro-Palestine students engaged in activism are multifaceted. While they may experience significant stress, anxiety, and emotional fatigue, they also find empowerment, hope, and a strong sense of community. Balancing these impacts is crucial for sustaining long-term engagement and maintaining personal wellbeing. Support systems, self-care practices, and mental health resources are essential to help these students navigate their activism's emotional and psychological challenges. Buheji (2020a)

The sense of community would start once someone participated in the street protests and then join the university sit-ins; they would actively participate more in demonstrations to voice their opposition to injustices. Then, they would call for divestment from companies and institutions that support oppressive regimes, using economic pressure as a tool for change. Here, these students can start to visualise parallels of change through other historical movements, such as the anti-apartheid struggle in South Africa; thus, they start to recognize the power of persistent activism and international solidarity.

Engagement in activism can also foster a strong sense of community and solidarity. Connecting with like-minded individuals provides emotional support and reduces feelings of isolation. The shared goal of fighting for justice has created strong bonds among activists, contributing to a supportive network that helps mitigate some of the negative psychological impacts.

Part of the mitigation strategy for avoiding psychological risks and building a further collective sense of community is to appreciate the value of the sacrifice these Gen-Z Pro-Palestine Students have made and its impact on the world. One can reflect this value by the constructs of the following formula that carries lots of meanings:

- a) The outcome of Sacrifice (in short- and long-term)
- b) Perceived Likelihood of Palestine Achievements due to this sacrifice

In relevance to:

- c) Time that would show the Change Done due to this sacrifice
- d) Further Sacrifice Efforts are needed to bring major FreePalestine Achievements.

$$\text{i.e. Value of Sacrifice} = (a \times b) / (c \times d)$$

This simply means that those Pro-Palestine Protesters started what is called by the change experts the butterfly effect, and no human power can stop this change.

If the sacrificing students realise this, they will be engulfed with a shield that will prevent them from 'resilience fatigue'.

The momentum for change is fuelled by peer influence, with peer students encouraging each other to join the cause and stand up for their beliefs. This cross-cultural solidarity extends beyond cultural and religious lines, with even Jewish students joining the protests against the policies of the Israeli government.

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